

Lunar ionosphere in the Geotail region as observed by Chandrayaan-2 Orbiter using two-way Radio Occultation measurements: Supplementary Section

KESHAV R. TRIPATHI ¹

¹Space Physics Laboratory (SPL), VSSC, ISRO, Trivandrum- 695022, Kerala, India

²JSPS International Research Fellow, The University of Tokyo, Japan.

ABSTRACT

The Supplementary section of the paper entitled “Lunar ionosphere in the Geotail region as observed by Chandrayaan-2 Orbiter using two-way Radio Occultation measurements” describes errors associated with the derived electron density profiles of the Moon obtained using two-way Radio Occultation (RO) experiments. It also provides details of the three-dimensional Ionospheric model used in the study to understand the source of the unreasonably high electron density in the Lunar ionosphere during a period when the Moon was inside the Earth’s magnetotail.

Keywords: Moon — planets and satellites: atmospheres — methods: data analysis — occultations

1. ERROR ASSOCIATED WITH THE OBSERVED ELECTRON DENSITY PROFILE

In the two-way Radio Occultation (RO) experiments discussed in this manuscript, the radio signals are produced by a stable MASER system on the ground, with a stability of around 10^{-15} over a 1000-second integration time. These signals are sent from the 32-meter diameter antenna at the Indian Deep Space Network (IDSN) in Bengaluru, India. The signals are phase-locked with an onboard oscillator on the Chandrayaan-2 (CH-2) orbiter and then transmitted back to a ground-based receiver. In a two-way RO experiment, the signal passes through the terrestrial atmosphere/ionosphere, interplanetary medium, and target medium twice. The errors in the phase of the radio signal due to these mediums are relatively higher than in one-way RO experiments. Even though we remove a constant DC bias in the phase of radio signals using baseline fitting, the small-scale fluctuations in the phase due to these mediums still affect the radio signal. In this work, we have used a method described in the subsequent section to measure the potential error associated with the frequency residual and thus the observed electron density profile.

1.1. *The true mean and standard deviation of the frequency residual*

We employed the Monte Carlo method to estimate the mean and standard deviation of observed frequency residuals on 8th November 2022. Since we lack precise information about the exact extent of the lunar ionosphere, we calculated multiple means and standard devi-

ations for the frequency residuals across varying altitude ranges between 90 km and 30 km. The upper limit was fixed at 90 km, while the lower limit was varied from 30 km to 50 km in 1 km intervals. This approach yielded several estimates of the mean and standard deviation. We then calculated the mean of the means and the mean of the standard deviations to determine the true mean and true standard deviation of frequency residuals outside the approximated lunar plasma medium. The decision to vary the lower altitude between 30 km and 50 km, thereby extending the estimated upper limit of the lunar ionosphere, was based on previous studies. (Imamura et al. 2012; Choudhary et al. 2016; Withers et al. 2021; Tripathi et al. 2022). The estimated errors at altitude ranges are given in the table-1.

The mean (m) and standard deviation (σ) values were employed to generate random Gaussian noise. These uncertainties were incorporated into the frequency residual time series to estimate the i TEC value along with its associated uncertainty, ultimately deriving the electron density profile. The red error bars in Figure 1 represent the 1σ uncertainties in the electron density profile across the altitudes.

1.2. *Error estimation using method suggested by Withers et. al., (2021)*

To estimate the errors in the electron density values presented in this work, we also utilized the equation (1) from Withers et al. (2021). This equation establishes a connection between the observed uncertainty in the frequency residual ($\sigma_{\Delta f}$) and the related uncertainty in the

Figure 1. The observed electron density profile (EDP) on November 8, 2022, is represented by the black curve. The blue error bars indicate uncertainties estimated using Withers’s method, while the red error bars represent the 1σ uncertainty, as described in the text.

electron density profile (σ_{Ne}). The equation is expressed as follows:

$$\sigma_{Ne} = \frac{4\pi\sigma_{\Delta f} f c m_e \epsilon_0}{|v|e^2} \sqrt{\frac{2\pi H}{R}} \quad (1)$$

Where, f: transmitted frequency : 2041.598×10^6 Hz
c: Speed of light in vacuum : 2.9979×10^5 km/s
 m_e : Mass of the electron : 9.1094×10^{-31} kg
 ϵ_0 : Permittivity of free Space : 8.8542×10^{-12} F/m
e: Coulomb charge : 1.6022×10^{-19} C
H = Scale height of the lunar ionosphere: 15 km (Withers et al. 2021)
R : Radius of the planet: 1737.4 km
|v|: Line of site (LOS) velocity : shown in left panel of the Figure-2.

We used this method too on the data set of frequency residuals obtained on 08 November 2022. The only time-varying component in this analysis is the variation in the Line of Sight (LOS) velocity, as shown in the left panel of Figure 2. The LOS velocity increases as tangent height (/impact parameter) of radio signals move away from the planet. Consequently, the respective variation in the uncertainty value of the electron density, which is inversely proportional to the LOS velocity, is shown in the right panel of Figure 2. To estimate the σ_{Ne} , the value of $\sigma_{\Delta f}$ has been calculated as the standard deviation of frequency residuals as described in previous

section, column-5 of the Table-1, which comes out as a constant at 0.01281 Hz for this experiment.

Figure 2, right panel shows that there is no significant variation in the σ_{Ne} , and remains almost constant within the ionosphere. The uncertainty observed by equation-1 is referred to as the uncertainty due to Withers method, while the uncertainty calculated from the method described in previous section is defined as the conventional method. In Figure 1, the uncertainties due to Withers’ Method and conventional method, described above, are represented by blue and red error bars, respectively. Withers’ method shows a higher uncertainty compared to the conventional method. However, the error estimated by both methods is smaller than the electron density values in the Lunar ionosphere.

2. THREE DIMENSIONAL LUNAR IONOSPHERIC MODEL (3D-LIM)

The latitudinal, longitudinal, and altitudinal distribution of the ion & electron density in the Lunar ionosphere was estimated using 3D-LIM by solving the ion and electron continuity equations. The model considers photoionization of ten neutrals namely CO_2 , H_2O , CO , CH_4 , OH , O , Ar , Ne , He , and H_2 . Figure 3 (left panel) shows the vertical distribution of the neutral density for 8 November 2022 (latitude: $74^\circ N$, longitude: $81^\circ W$, Solar Zenith Angle: 88° , Local Time: 6:30 hrs).

Figure 2. Left panel: Variation of the line of site velocity with altitude in the ionosphere. Right panel: Altitude variation of the uncertainty in the electron density profile using Withers method.

The model also includes ionization by photo dissociative reactions and photoelectron impact. The charge exchange reactions of primary ions with neutrals, and dissociative/radiative recombination reactions of molecular and atomic ions used in the present study are listed in the Tables below. Essentially, the model considers the production and loss reactions of 16 ions, namely, CO_2^+ , CO^+ , C^+ , H_2O^+ , H_3O^+ , OH^+ , O_2^+ , O^+ , Ar^+ , Ne^+ , He^+ , H^+ , H_2^+ , CH_3^+ , CH_4^+ , and CH_5^+ . Other model details are available elsewhere (?).

In the present study, since the Moon is inside the magnetosphere, one component that adds ion/electron density to the background plasma is the charge exchange reactions with the magnetospheric particle flux. The tables below show the charge exchange rate/frequency of these reactions. To account for the diffusion of ions/electrons along the geomagnetic field line, the ion/electron density was calculated using the equation from equation 17 in (Daily et al. 1977), $n_i = \frac{P_i \times H_n}{V_i}$, where n_i is the i^{th} ion density, P_i is the production rate of the ion, V_i is the bulk velocity of the ion and H_n is the neutral scale height. While calculating the bulk velocity, the temperature of the ion was assumed to be the background neutral temperature. The electron temperature was taken as 2000 K.

Figure 3 (right panel) shows the vertical distribution of the ion and electron density in the presence of magnetic field diffusion and magnetospheric charge exchange reactions. In this case, major ions are molecular ions such as H_2O^+ , CO_2^+ , OH^+ . However, when the electron density is high and comparable with the observed value, the 3D-LIM considered the ionosphere is in photochemical equilibrium and the magnetospheric charge exchange reactions are absent. In this case, major ions are inert gas ions as given in Figure 3 (middle panel).

Dissociative/Radiative recombination reactions, ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$)

Reaction	Rate Coefficient
$\text{CO}_2^+ + e^- \rightarrow \text{CO} + \text{O}$	$6.5 \times 10^{-7} (300/T_e)^{0.8}$
$\text{H}_2\text{O}^+ + e^- \rightarrow \text{O} + 2\text{H}$	$3.1 \times 10^{-7} (300/T_e)^{0.5}$
$\text{O}^+ + e^- \rightarrow \text{O} + h\nu$	$3.5 \times 10^{-12} (300/T_e)^{0.7}$
$\text{O}_2^+ + e^- \rightarrow \text{O} + \text{O}$	$1.9 \times 10^{-7} (300/T_e)^{0.7}$
$\text{OH}^+ + e^- \rightarrow \text{O} + \text{H}$	$3.7 \times 10^{-8} (300/T_e)^{0.5}$
$\text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + e^- \rightarrow 2\text{H} + \text{OH}$	$3.1 \times 10^{-7} (300/T_e)^{0.5}$
$\text{CO}^+ + e^- \rightarrow \text{C} + \text{O}$	$1.0 \times 10^{-7} (300/T_e)^{0.46}$
$\text{C}^+ + e^- \rightarrow \text{C} + h\nu$	$3.5 \times 10^{-12} (300/T_e)^{0.7}$
$\text{H}^+ + e^- \rightarrow \text{H} + h\nu$	$4.8 \times 10^{-12} (250/T_e)^{0.7}$
$\text{H}_2^+ + e^- \rightarrow \text{H} + \text{H}$	$1.6 \times 10^{-8} (300/T_e)^{0.43}$
$\text{CH}_4^+ + e^- \rightarrow \text{CH}_3 + \text{H}$	$6.0 \times 10^{-7} (300/T_e)^{0.5}$
$\text{CH}_3^+ + e^- \rightarrow \text{CH}_2 + \text{H}$	$3.5 \times 10^{-7} (300/T_e)^{0.5}$
$\text{CH}_5^+ + e^- \rightarrow \text{CH}_4 + \text{H}$	$8.0 \times 10^{-7} (300/T_e)^{0.5}$
$\text{Ar}^+ + e^- \rightarrow \text{Ar} + h\nu$	$4.8 \times 10^{-12} (250/T_e)^{0.7}$
$\text{He}^+ + e^- \rightarrow \text{He} + h\nu$	$4.8 \times 10^{-12} (250/T_e)^{0.7}$
$\text{Ne}^+ + e^- \rightarrow \text{Ne} + h\nu$	$4.8 \times 10^{-12} (250/T_e)^{0.7}$

Figure 3. Left panel : vertical distribution of neutral density used in the model; Middle panel : vertical ion density distribution when diffusion is absent ; Right panel : vertical ion density distribution when diffusion is included in the model

Charge exchange reactions, ($\text{cm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$)

Reaction	Rate Coefficient
$\text{CO}_2^+ + \text{O} \rightarrow \text{O}_2^+ + \text{CO}$	1.6×10^{-10}
$\text{CO}_2^+ + \text{O} \rightarrow \text{CO}_2 + \text{O}^+$	9.6×10^{-11}
$\text{CO}_2^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}^+ + \text{CO}_2$	1.7×10^{-9}
$\text{CO}_2^+ + \text{CH}_4 \rightarrow \text{CH}_4^+ + \text{CO}_2$	5.5×10^{-10}
$\text{H}_2\text{O}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \text{OH}$	2.0×10^{-9}
$\text{H}_2\text{O}^+ + \text{OH} \rightarrow \text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \text{O}$	6.9×10^{-10}
$\text{H}_2\text{O}^+ + \text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \text{H}$	7.6×10^{-10}
$\text{H}_2\text{O}^+ + \text{CH}_4 \rightarrow \text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \text{CH}_3$	1.12×10^{-9}
$\text{O}^+ + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{O}_2^+ + \text{CO}$	9.4×10^{-10}
$\text{O}^+ + \text{OH} \rightarrow \text{H}^+ + \text{O}_2$	7.2×10^{-10}
$\text{O}^+ + \text{OH} \rightarrow \text{OH}^+ + \text{O}$	3.6×10^{-10}
$\text{O}^+ + \text{CH}_4 \rightarrow \text{CH}_3^+ + \text{OH}$	1.10×10^{-10}
$\text{O}^+ + \text{OH} \rightarrow \text{H} + \text{O}_2^+$	3.6×10^{-10}
$\text{O}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}^+ + \text{O}$	2.5×10^{-9}
$\text{O}^+ + \text{CH}_4 \rightarrow \text{CH}_4^+ + \text{O}$	8.9×10^{-10}
$\text{OH}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}^+ + \text{OH}$	1.6×10^{-9}
$\text{OH}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \text{O}$	1.3×10^{-9}
$\text{OH}^+ + \text{CH}_4 \rightarrow \text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \text{CH}_2$	1.4×10^{-9}

Charge exchange reactions, ($\text{cm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$)

Reaction	Rate Coefficient
$\text{OH}^+ + \text{OH} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}^+ + \text{O}$	7.0×10^{-10}
$\text{OH}^+ + \text{O} \rightarrow \text{O}_2^+ + \text{H}$	1.0×10^{-9}
$\text{He}^+ + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}^+ + \text{O} + \text{He}$	7.8×10^{-10}
$\text{He}^+ + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO} + \text{O}^+ + \text{He}$	1.4×10^{-10}
$\text{He}^+ + \text{CH}_4 \rightarrow \text{CH}_4^+ + \text{He}$	5.10×10^{-11}
$\text{He}^+ + \text{CH}_4 \rightarrow \text{CH}_3^+ + \text{H} + \text{He}$	8.5×10^{-11}
$\text{He}^+ + \text{CH}_4 \rightarrow \text{CH}_3 + \text{He} + \text{H}^+$	4.8×10^{-10}
$\text{H}_2^+ + \text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{H}_3^+ + \text{H}$	2.0×10^{-9}
$\text{H}_2^+ + \text{CH}_4 \rightarrow \text{CH}_3^+ + \text{H} + \text{H}_2$	3.8×10^{-9}
$\text{H}_2^+ + \text{CH}_4 \rightarrow \text{CH}_4^+ + \text{H}_2$	1.4×10^{-9}
$\text{H}_3^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \text{H}_2$	5.3×10^{-9}
$\text{H}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}^+ + \text{H}$	8.2×10^{-9}
$\text{H}^+ + \text{O} \rightarrow \text{O}^+ + \text{H}$	3.75×10^{-10}
$\text{H}^+ + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}_2^+ + \text{H}$	4.2×10^{-9}
$\text{H}^+ + \text{OH} \rightarrow \text{OH}^+ + \text{H}$	1.0×10^{-9}
$\text{H}^+ + \text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{H}_2^+ + \text{H}$	1.0×10^{-9}
$\text{H}^+ + \text{CH}_4 \rightarrow \text{CH}_3^+ + \text{H}_2$	2.3×10^{-9}
$\text{H}^+ + \text{CH}_4 \rightarrow \text{CH}_4^+ + \text{H}$	1.5×10^{-9}
$\text{CO}^+ + \text{O} \rightarrow \text{CO} + \text{O}^+$	1.4×10^{-10}
$\text{CO}^+ + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}_2^+ + \text{CO}$	9.6×10^{-10}
$\text{CO}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}^+ + \text{CO}$	1.7×10^{-9}
$\text{CO}^+ + \text{OH} \rightarrow \text{OH}^+ + \text{CO}$	3.2×10^{-10}
$\text{CO}^+ + \text{CH}_4 \rightarrow \text{CH}_4^+ + \text{CO}$	7.93×10^{-10}
$\text{C}^+ + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}^+ + \text{CO}$	9.9×10^{-10}
$\text{C}^+ + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}_2^+ + \text{C}$	1.1×10^{-10}
$\text{C}^+ + \text{OH} \rightarrow \text{CO}^+ + \text{H}$	1.1×10^{-10}
$\text{CH}_4^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \text{CH}_3$	2.5×10^{-9}
$\text{CH}_4^+ + \text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{H} + \text{CH}_5^+$	3.5×10^{-11}
$\text{CH}_4^+ + \text{CH}_4 \rightarrow \text{CH}_3 + \text{CH}_5^+$	1.5×10^{-9}
$\text{CH}_4^+ + \text{O} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3^+ + \text{OH}$	1.0×10^{-9}

Table 1. Uncertainty in observed frequency residual

Range	Mean (m)	std*(σ)	True Mean (m)	True std (σ)
30.0	-0.000114	0.013111		
31.0	-0.000157	0.013080		
32.0	-0.000195	0.013051		
33.0	-0.000224	0.013029		
34.0	-0.000254	0.013005		
35.0	-0.000279	0.012982		
36.0	-0.000299	0.012962		
37.0	-0.000318	0.012940		
38.0	-0.000337	0.012914		
39.0	-0.000355	0.012885	-0.000309	0.01281
40.0	-0.000372	0.012852		
41.0	-0.000385	0.012818		
42.0	-0.000394	0.012782		
43.0	-0.000395	0.012744		
44.0	-0.000389	0.012708		
45.0	-0.000376	0.012667		
46.0	-0.000360	0.012623		
47.0	-0.000342	0.012569		
48.0	-0.000330	0.012512		
49.0	-0.000318	0.012453		
50.0	-0.000300	0.012379		

*std: standard deviation

Charge exchange reactions with magnetospheric protons

Charge exchange rate / frequency for an average density of 10 particles cm^3 and speed of 100 km/s.

Reaction	Production frequency (s^{-1})
$\text{H}^+ + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}_2^+ + \text{H}$	1.51×10^{-7}
$\text{H}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}^+ + \text{H}$	1.44×10^{-7}
$\text{H}^+ + \text{O} \rightarrow \text{O}^+ + \text{H}$	6.5×10^{-8}
$\text{H}^+ + \text{OH} \rightarrow \text{OH}^+ + \text{H}$	2.2×10^{-7}
$\text{H}^+ + \text{Ar} \rightarrow \text{Ar}^+ + \text{H}$	1.5×10^{-7}
$\text{H}^+ + \text{He} \rightarrow \text{He}^+ + \text{H}$	4.18×10^{-11}
$\text{H}^+ + \text{Ne} \rightarrow \text{Ne}^+ + \text{H}$	6.08×10^{-10}

Magnetospheric electron impact ionization reactions

(Electron density 5 cm^{-3} and electron temperature of $1.5 \times 10^5 \text{ K}$)

Reaction	Production frequency/flux ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$)
$\text{e}^- + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}_2^+ + \text{e}^- + \text{e}^-$	8.32×10^{-9}
$\text{e}^- + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}^+ + \text{e}^- + \text{e}^-$	1.18×10^{-8}
$\text{e}^- + \text{O} \rightarrow \text{O}^+ + \text{e}^- + \text{e}^-$	5.03×10^{-9}
$\text{e}^- + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{OH}^+ + \text{H} + \text{e}^- + \text{e}^-$	2.17×10^{-9}
$\text{e}^- + \text{Ar} \rightarrow \text{Ar}^+ + \text{e}^- + \text{e}^-$	2.40×10^{-8}
$\text{e}^- + \text{He} \rightarrow \text{He}^+ + \text{e}^- + \text{e}^-$	1.70×10^{-9}
$\text{e}^- + \text{Ne} \rightarrow \text{Ne}^+ + \text{e}^- + \text{e}^-$	9.70×10^{-9}
$\text{e}^- + \text{CO} \rightarrow \text{CO}^+ + \text{e}^- + \text{e}^-$	7.38×10^{-9}
$\text{e}^- + \text{CH}_4 \rightarrow \text{CH}_4^+ + \text{e}^- + \text{e}^-$	5.03×10^{-9}

REFERENCES

Choudhary, R. K., Ambili, K. M., Choudhury, S., Dhanya, M. B., & Bhardwaj, A. 2016, Geophysical Research Letters, 43, 10

Daily, W. D., Barker, W. A., Clark, M., Dyal, P., & Parkin, C. W. 1977, Journal of Geophysical Research, 82, 5441

Photo-ionization reactions, s^{-1}

Reaction	Rate Coefficient*	Reference
$\text{CO}_2 + h\nu \rightarrow \text{CO}_2^+ + e^-$	1.04×10^{-6}	Calculated in this work
$\text{H}_2\text{O} + h\nu \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}^+ + e^-$	5.51×10^{-7}	Calculated in this work
$\text{OH} + h\nu \rightarrow \text{OH}^+ + e^-$	3.87×10^{-7}	Calculated in this work
$\text{CO} + h\nu \rightarrow \text{CO}^+ + e^-$	7.11×10^{-7}	Calculated in this work
$\text{O} + h\nu \rightarrow \text{O}^+ + e^-$	4.47×10^{-7}	Calculated in this work
$\text{He} + h\nu \rightarrow \text{He}^+ + e^-$	1.16×10^{-7}	Calculated in this work
$\text{H}_2 + h\nu \rightarrow \text{H}_2^+ + e^-$	1.34×10^{-7}	Calculated in this work
$\text{Ar} + h\nu \rightarrow \text{Ar}^+ + e^-$	6.05×10^{-7}	Calculated in this work
$\text{Ne} + h\nu \rightarrow \text{Ne}^+ + e^-$	3.75×10^{-7}	Calculated in this work
$\text{CH}_4 + h\nu \rightarrow \text{CH}_4^+ + e^-$	1.22×10^{-6}	Calculated in this work

*The production frequencies correspond to the latitude, longitude, SZA and the local time of the present study at 5 km

Photo dissociative ionization reactions, s^{-1}

Reaction	Rate Coefficient*	Reference
$\text{CO}_2 + h\nu \rightarrow \text{O}^+ + \text{CO} + e^-$	1.03×10^{-7}	Calculated in this work
$\text{CO}_2 + h\nu \rightarrow \text{CO}^+ + \text{O} + e^-$	6.27×10^{-8}	Calculated in this work
$\text{CO}_2 + h\nu \rightarrow \text{C}^+ + \text{O}_2 + e^-$	4.74×10^{-8}	Calculated in this work
$\text{H}_2\text{O} + h\nu \rightarrow \text{H} + \text{OH}^+ + e^-$	1.14×10^{-7}	Calculated in this work
$\text{H}_2\text{O} + h\nu \rightarrow \text{H}_2 + \text{O}^+ + e^-$	7.39×10^{-9}	Calculated in this work
$\text{H}_2\text{O} + h\nu \rightarrow \text{H}^+ + \text{OH} + e^-$	5.31×10^{-8}	Calculated in this work
$\text{H}_2 + h\nu \rightarrow \text{H}^+ + \text{H} + e^-$	3.22×10^{-9}	Calculated in this work
$\text{CO} + h\nu \rightarrow \text{C}^+ + \text{O} + e^-$	4.34×10^{-8}	Calculated in this work
$\text{CO} + h\nu \rightarrow \text{O}^+ + \text{C} + e^-$	1.01×10^{-7}	Calculated in this work
$\text{CH}_4 + h\nu \rightarrow \text{CH}_3^+ + \text{H} + e^-$	3.14×10^{-7}	Calculated in this work
$\text{CH}_4 + h\nu \rightarrow \text{CH}_3 + \text{H}^+ + e^-$	1.45×10^{-8}	Calculated in this work

Imamura, T., Nabatov, A., Mochizuki, N., et al. 2012,
Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics, 117
Tripathi, K. R., Choudhary, R. K., Ambili, K. M., et al.
2022, Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical
Society: Letters, 515, L61

Withers, P., Stubbs, T. J., & Mazarico, E. 2021, Advances
in Space Research, 67, 4099